

Extended release of Metronidazole using Montmorillonite as drug delivery vehicle[†]

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Abstract : In the present work Montmorillonite (Mt) has been explored as a drug delivery vehicle for an antibiotic drug, Metronidazole (MTZ). The drug Mt interaction has been studied as a function of pH of the aqueous drug solution, contact time and initial drug concentration in the solution. The synthesized Mt-MTZ complex has been characterized using various appropriate analytical techniques. The *in vitro* release of MTZ from the synthesized Mt-MTZ complex in the simulated gastric fluid has been observed to provide more retention than the pure drug and the commercially available tablets. In the simulated intestinal fluid Mt-MTZ complex has been observed to provide better extended release of MTZ as compared to the pure drug and the commercially available tablets. The synthesized Mt-MTZ complex is more acidic resistant and provides an increase bioavailability in the intestinal fluid over an extended period of 12 h. The synthesized Mt-MTZ complex is likely to provide about three times more bioavailability of the drug as compare to pure MTZ.

Keywords : Adsorption, extended release, Metronidazole, Montmorillonite.

Introduction

Metronidazole (MTZ) is marketed under the brand name of Flagyl and is effective in the treatment of anaerobic infection^{1,2}. It is used either alone or in combination with other antibiotic. It is effective in to guinea worm disease, giardiasis, amoebiasis etc.^{3,4}. Metronidazole (Flagyl) at present can be administered in oral and intravenous form.

In order to prevent antibiotic resistance, it is recommended to have frequent administration of conventional formulation (with short half-life) so that the concentration of the drug under MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) is not likely to occur. Hence, it is desirable to maintain a greater than MIC drug concentration in the plasma for a prolonged period of time. Therefore, oral extended release dose form can maximise the therapeutic effect of antibiotics while minimizing the antibiotic resistance along with improved patient compliance⁵.

In the present work Montmorillonite (Mt), belonging to Smectite group^{6,7} of clay, has been explored as a delivery vehicle for Metronidazole.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

Metronidazole (2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole-1-ethanol) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich, USA. Analytical grade, ortho-phosphoric acid, HCl, KCl, NaOH, KH₂PO₄ was procured from MERCK (Germany). HPLC grade methanol, acetonitrile and water were used for the estimation of MTZ by HPLC technique.

Experimental :

Absorption spectrum of the drug as a function of pH (4.0 to 10) indicates no change at any of the pH value (Fig. 1). Therefore, quantitative estimation of the drug was performed at 320 nm and the pH of the solution was maintained at pH 4.

Extraction efficiency of MTZ as a function of pH, contact time and initial concentration of the drug in the solution :

The effect of pH and contact time on extraction efficiency was performed with 25 mL of 40 mg L⁻¹ drug solution. The maximum uptake was observed at pH 2 therefore, extraction efficiency as a function of time was

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectra of aqueous solution of MTZ as a function of pH.

performed at pH 2. Contact time of 40 min was found to be optimum. Hence, extraction efficiency as a function of initial concentration of the drug was performed at pH 2 for duration of 40 min (Fig. 2). The Mt drug complex obtained under these conditions ($> 60 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) was used for characterisation and *in vitro* drug release studies.

Fig. 2. Extraction efficiencies of MTZ as a function of the pH of the drug solution, contact time of extraction and the initial concentration of the drug in the solution.

Results and discussion

In case of Mt-drug complex the characteristic diffraction peak of Mt was observed at 2θ value of 6.7° (d spacing of 13.12 \AA) suggesting intercalation of the drug molecule in an orientation which results in decrease in d spacing as compared to the Mt with hydrated interlayer cations (d spacing of 17.16 \AA).

Further, there seems to be no observable change in the surface morphology (SEM) of Mt-MTZ complex as

compared to the pristine Mt (Fig. 3) which supports the XRD data.

Release profile (*in vitro*) of the Metronidazole :

In vitro release profile of pure drug and Mt-drug complex was carried out in the simulated intestinal fluid (PBS, pH 7.4) and in the gastric fluid (HCl, pH 1.2) using dialysis bag method^{8,9} for a period of 12 h. Buffer solution of gastric fluid was prepared by the reported procedure^{10,11}. A known amount of the pure drug, commercial tablets and the synthesized Mt-MTZ complex was kept in the dialysis bag with 5 mL of buffer solution following the reported procedure^{10,11}. The concentration of the drug in each sample was estimated using HPLC technique with UV-Visible spectrometer as the detector. The cumulative percentage of drug released was calculated. 76% and 98% of pure MTZ was released within 6 h in the gastric fluid and 3.5 h in the intestinal fluid respectively. In case of commercial tablets, 75% and 66% of MTZ was released in the gastric and intestinal fluid respectively over a period of 12 h.

Fig. 3. SEM images of the pristine Mt (A) and Mt-MTZ complex (B).

Arun Kant *et al.* : Extended release of Metronidazole using Montmorillonite as drug delivery vehicle

Fig. 4. Cumulative drug release profile of pure MTZ, commercial tablets 1 and 2 and Mt drug complex in the gastric fluid (A) and in the intestinal fluid (B).

However, the synthesised Mt-MTZ complex was observed to release the drug in an extended manner, 27% and 97% in the gastric and intestinal fluid respectively over a period of 12 h (Fig. 4).

Conclusion

In the present work a new class of Mt-MTZ complex was successfully synthesised for the extended release (*in vitro*) of an antibiotics drug, Metronidazole. In order to prevent antibiotic resistance, it is recommended to have frequent administration of conventional formulation (with short half-life) so that the concentration of the drug under MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) is not likely to occur.

In vitro drug release data of the present work suggest that the synthesized Mt-drug complex is able to retain the high amount of MTZ in gastric media as compared to the pure drug with the advantage of gradual drug release over a longer period of time in the simulated intestinal fluid thus, having the potential of reducing the multiple dosing and helping in maintaining the desirable concentration of the drug in plasma.

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